

Qualification Profile for Youth Work

Competence Requirements of full-time Professionals in Youth Work

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Context of the Qualification Profile for Youth Work

Child and youth work¹ is an important field of socialisation for children and adolescents, which offers them possibilities for self-created, diverse educational processes. Voluntary work is still a significant characteristic of youth work, but at the same time it has been a socio-pedagogical field of work for quite some time and it would be impossible without full-time professionals. The fields of activity of full-time professionals include areas such as local community and communal youth welfare, open youth work and youth work in clubs, street work and mobile youth work or also the work at adventure and active playgrounds, in youth education institutes and youth associations.

The professionals face similar challenges in all these areas of action. On the one hand, they result from the increased social expectations regarding youth work. On the other hand, they result from the specifics of youth work. At the same time, they are the decisive context for the socio-pedagogical competences required in the field of youth work. The present Qualification Profile for Youth Work takes this perspective and frames the competence requirements that are expected from full-time professionals in youth work today.

¹ Hereinafter the term youth work will be used. Even though the term children and youth work is used increasingly often and the expansion of the target group is thereby made more visible, the usage of the term is based on the description in § 11 Sozialgesetzbuch VIII (Social Code) (hereinafter called SGB VIII).

Youth work – a demanding field of work

Youth work is a highly complex and, at the same time, very diverse field of work. It is mainly defined by its fundamental principles and the lack of legal definition. The legal provision, that “the required programmes for youth work, that are necessary for promoting the development of young people, have to be made available for them, be adapted to the interests of young people and are co-created and shaped by them, enable them to be self-determined and to take social responsibility and (should) motivate and lead them towards social commitment” (transl. from German original), makes youth work a very dynamic and also diverse field of work (§ 11 para.1 SGB VIII (Social Code)). In accordance with the principles of youth work such as voluntariness, openness and participation, the result is that the field of work is subject to constant change, depending on developments in young people’s

living conditions, social expectations and the concrete interests of the participants. Along with this goes the necessity to constantly negotiate and adapt the offers. In addition, the requirements on full-time youth work professionals have continued to increase, especially due to social developments and processes of change over the last few years and their effects on adolescents’ living environments (cf. Bundesjugendkuratorium 2017 (Federal Youth Board)). Nowadays, regardless of each specific area of activity of full-time professionals, youth work is an extraordinary demanding field of work. The Qualification Profile for Youth Work demonstrates these manifold requirements.

The potential of competence orientation for youth work

The perspective of the Qualification Profile for Youth Work is oriented along the descriptions of the “Deutscher Qualifikationsrahmen für lebenslanges Lernen (DQR)” (German qualification framework for life-long learning) and is linked to the “Hochschulischer Qualifikationsrahmen (HQR)” (Qualification framework of higher education) and the “Qualifikationsrahmen Sozialer Arbeit (QR SozArb)” (Qualification framework for social work).² The DQR describes on eight levels to what extent capabilities and skills were acquired in different educational measures or processes. To this end, the knowledge, the skills, the autonomy and the social competence are described in more detail in the categories “competence in the field” and “personal competence”. The systematic illustration and classification of education and further training in qualification

frameworks increases the openness between higher / school education and vocational training and enables transparency and recognition of non-formally and informally acquired competences. Establishing competence frameworks has the potential, especially for youth work professionals, to make competences that were often acquired non-formally and informally visible and promote their recognition in higher / school education. The Qualification Profile for Youth Work follows on from these developments and is an active reaction to the challenges that result for professionals, employers and higher education institutions from the qualification framework.

² DQR: www.dqr.de;
HQR: www.hrk.de/fileadmin/redaktion/hrk/02-Dokumente/02-03-Studium/02-03-02-Qualifikationsrahmen/2017_Qualifikationsrahmen_HQR.pdf;
QR SozArb: www.fbts-ev.de/qualifikationsrahmen-soziale-arbeit

The project context of the Qualification Profile for Youth Work

The Qualification Profile for Youth Work is the result of the project "Theorie-Praxis-Austausch zum professionellen Selbstverständnis der Jugendarbeit (TPA_SJ)" (Theory-practice exchange for the professional self-conception of youth work), a sub-project of the research project "Jugendarbeit und Bildung - Implementierung in den Studiengang Soziale Arbeit (JuB_Imp_So)" (Youth work and education – Implementation in the social work course) at the university of Kempten. The formulation process is founded on a broad empirical basis: Eight group interviews with representatives of different areas of youth work in Bavaria were conducted and evaluated with qualitative content-analysis (cf. Riechert, e.g. 2018). The results were discussed and commented on during a continuous intensive exchange process with further stakeholders in youth work from the fields of science, theory, education, practice and politics.³ The formulation process provides essential momentum for addressing the issue of quality in youth work. The importance is stressed repeatedly, for example with the following justification:

"Without an open debate about the question, what the indispensable core elements of a professional qualification profile are and how they can be guaranteed, the efforts for the professionalisation of youth work will reach its limits and eventually fail." (Hafeneger 2013, p. 428, transl.)

Not only the development process but also the present result should continue to inspire an open discussion between different stakeholders of youth work and promote the professional self-assurance.

³ The creation process was supported by the Bavarian Youth Council KdöR which promoted it and thereby particularly increased the popularity of the project within the field of youth work. Following in on the Qualification Profile for Youth Work, a quantitative study about the significance of selected competences from the perspective of children's and youth work professionals was conducted (cf. Rottach 2018).

The characterisation and objective of the Qualification Profile for Youth Work

The Qualification Profile for Youth Work describes what is to be understood by qualitatively appropriate and professionally recognised action in youth work. In this context, the focus does not lie on the development of youth work that is called professionalisation (e.g. occupationalisation), but on the actions of each individual person (cf. Nittel 2011). Thus, the present qualification profile shows, from a competence-oriented perspective, which skills and capabilities full-time professionals need in order to be able to adequately deal with the specific task structures and challenges in youth work. It can be characterised according to the following aspects, putting the aforementioned objective into concrete terms.

- **Empirically discursive:** Empirically discursive: The starting point of the formulation process were group interviews with representatives from different areas of activity in youth work in Bavaria (Open Youth Work, streetwork/ mobile youth work, adventure and active playgrounds, local community youth work, communal youth care, youth clubs, youth associations, youth education institutes). The results of the evaluation were discussed in a discursive process, in particular in workshops and con-

ventions of the TPA_SJ. Thereby, the perspective of further stakeholders in youth work was broached and considered in the creation of the Qualification Profile for Youth Work. Hence, the present result has an empirical foundation and at the same time was further developed discursively.

- **Generalising and specific:** The qualification profile takes up a generalising perspective on the field of youth work and the competences needed in this field and, therefore, draws abstract conclusions from the individual work areas with their respective particularities, e.g. the Open Youth Work or youth work in associations. This perspective is considered to be promising due to the specifics that youth work and the current social challenges have in common. At the same time, youth work is considered to be a specific field of social work, whereby the competence requirements for professionals in socio-pedagogical youth work require that a specification is created in the framework of social work.
- **Focus as a professional occupation:** The focus purposely lies on the full-time professionals in youth work and the competences required of them. The special relevance of voluntary work for youth work and the competences of volunteers are not thereby put into question, but they are not the focus of the present qualification profile.
- **Processual:** Not least because of the dynamics of youth work itself, the issue of qualifications should always lead to discussions. The relevance of an open discussion was explained above. With this in mind, the Qualification Profile for Youth Work is to be understood as processual as it can always serve as a stimulus for exchange between different areas of work, scientists, teachers and representatives of areas of work and provide an impetus for joint reflection on the current challenges in the field of youth work. Accordingly, the qualification profile is considered processual and, ultimately, open-ended.
- **Systematically competence-oriented:** The qualification profile systematically bundles the necessary competences and connects with prior qualification frameworks and their systematisation, in particular the "HQR" and the "QR SozArb". The qualification profile is based on a processual understanding of the skills acquisition and its continuous updating. Professionalism and professionally-qualified action continue to be a challenge and a never-ending project for each individual.

The structure of the Qualification Profile for Youth Work

The foundation of the Qualification Profile for Youth Work are the particularities of the field of youth work which are described separately. Apart from that, in accordance with the structure of the HQR, it is divided into four competence areas that are each subdivided into different competence dimensions. An overview in the form of a graphic illustration, in which the different areas are colour-coded, can be found in the middle of the brochure. The descriptions of the competences relate to level 6 of the DQR and are to be located on the level that is equivalent to the bachelors degree. This is due to the complexity of the field of work and the high standards that are applied to the full-time youth work professionals.

The Qualification Profile for Youth Work

Particularities of youth work

Particularities that shape the field of youth work overall result from youth work and its key characteristics. They form the specific context of professionally competent action. Particularly the following aspects are to be mentioned:

- **Voluntariness:** Limited “institutional, i.e. formal means of power” of the employees result from the voluntariness of the programmes (Schwerthelm e.g. 2015, p. 5).
- **Openness and discursivity:** Consistent negotiation processes and decision-making procedures go along with the openness not only regarding the topics but also regarding the participants of youth work. This can be described as “conditions of discontinuity” (cf. *ibid*).
- **Socio-pedagogical arena:** A specific aspect here is the negotiation of the relationships between participants, volunteers and full-time employees that lack general definitions. The term “socio-pedagogical arena” particularly stresses the negotiating of the mutual recognition (cf. Cloos e.g 2009).
- **Diffuse responsibility:** Not least the proactive orientation of youth work that is targeted at all adolescents, the vague remit and the different, changing expectations towards professionals lead to a diffuse distribution of responsibility (cf. Behr e.g. 2004, cf. Scherr 2003).
- **Readiness to act situationally:** What is meant is the simultaneity and the quick change from decentralised to centralised interaction, between participation and withdrawal, between action and rest, that require professionals to act situationally (cf. Thole 2003).
- **Freedom and necessity to create:** Youth work professionals usually have the freedom to co-create, concretise and continually adapt the focus and the tasks of their work. For the professionals, this freedom to create means simultaneously a necessity to create.

Operational competences

Pedagogically professional action, political action and administrative action / organisational management are the core dimensions of professional competence of youth work professionals. Each of these is an ongoing process: based on vast and integrated knowledge, professional tasks are described, analysed and assessed, measures are planned, conceptualised and, after they have been implemented, they undergo a process of reflection and evaluation. In the context of a complex and dynamic structure of requirements, professionals direct processes autonomously, particularly as regards the aspects mentioned below.

Qualification Profile for Youth Work Operational competences Pedagogically professional action

1. Facilitating participation

Youth work professionals are able to promote participation processes of children, adolescents and young adults by:

- comprehending participation as a basic principle and as a constantly changing organisational task in their work
- identifying and using opportunities to participate in their everyday life
- establishing structures and framework conditions for participation and living a positive culture of participation
- being able to adapt methods of participation in a situational way
- constantly reflecting on the current practice of participation

2. Shaping educational areas and processes

In line with the requirements described in § 11 SGB VIII, youth work professionals create diverse opportunities for (self-)education of children, adolescents and young adults by:

- continually striking a balance between freedom for adolescents and a pedagogical framework depending on the occasion
- considering young people's living-environmental, socio-spatial and everyday cultural contexts and situationally identifying occasions for education and making use of them
- creating accessible spaces to try things out for the individual personality development and chances for acquisition of personal, social and cultural competences (in the sense of empowerment didactics)
- (further) developing, negotiating and implementing pedagogical (framework) concepts for different contexts and levels (concerning duration, degree of structuredness etc.)
- developing and offering group-pedagogical, clique- and community-oriented programmes and projects
- drawing on selected pedagogical approaches (for example from sports, culture, experiential, environmental, political education)

3. Being a reliable confidante

Youth work professionals act as trustworthy contact persons for children, adolescents and young adults as well as for (voluntary) multipliers by:

- basing their actions on a reflected relationship between proximity and distance and recognising it as an essential pedagogical area of tension
- proposing and maintaining reliable and calculable relationships
- providing individual pedagogical counselling, mentoring and support in manifold situations, particularly in everyday situations, may they be familiar or unplanned
- assuming a mediating, clarifying role in conflicts

4. Creating professional cooperation

Youth work professionals contribute to the creation of points of contact by:

- supporting volunteer structures and shaping cooperation between volunteers and full-time workers
- organising the professional collaboration with (social) institutions as well as stakeholders within and outside of youth work and participating in cross-linked overall concepts
- knowing the specific characteristics and limits of their own personal responsibility, participating in support processes and referring to other professionals from other areas according to the situation
- professionally representing pedagogical action in youth work towards the public, parents, social organisations and initiatives, public authorities and cooperation partners
- offering their expert knowledge and contributing it to professional exchange

Qualification Profile for Youth Work Operational competences Political action

1. Advocating interests and participation of adolescents (lobbying)

Youth work professionals actively advocate the interests, needs and participation of children, adolescents and young adults in different levels of society by:

- creating and entrenching different possibilities for political participation of young people in the community
- gathering information about their specific needs and interests as comprehensively as possible to obtain the legitimacy for an attorney's mandate and repeatedly questioning this mandate
- advocating adolescents' rights, interests and issues based on the different living conditions and needs as well as on current social challenges and thereby providing translation work
- actively contributing their expert knowledge to the political discourse and initiating and accompanying policy-making processes in a partial manner for young people
- effectively raising public awareness, i.a. with the help of the media and campaigns, thereby contributing to the creation of more positive living conditions

2. Enabling adolescents to participate politically

Youth work professionals empower children, adolescents and young adults according to their legal duty (§ 11 SGB VIII) to participate politically and to commit socially by:

- creating access to information (for example, about their rights) as well as discussing political decision-making processes with them in a critical manner
- supporting them in developing reflected opinions as a basis for decision-making
- living participation as a fundamental attitude and democratic values in everyday youth work
- motivating young adults to contribute their opinions and views in the social dialogue and to take opportunities of participation in social processes

3. Creating and defending open spaces

Youth work professionals stand up for public, semi-public and institutionalised open spaces for children, adolescents and young adults by:

- being aware of the relevance of purpose-free spaces for personality development
- advocating their significance in political decision-making processes and defending these open spaces, if necessary
- reflecting on the processes of spatial appropriation of young adults together and supporting them in entering into constructive dialogue concerning this matter
- creating and designing these open spaces together with the young adults

4. Representing the field of youth work

Youth work professionals represent their field of work and issues concerning the same by:

- being aware of the significance of youth work and reflecting on it repeatedly and critically
- advocating the visibility and importance of youth work and representing the same (i.a. by participating in youth services planning and in other political processes)
- positioning themselves within social work and representing the professionalism and specifics of youth work

5. Representing interests concerning labour policy

Youth work professionals position themselves concerning labour policy by:

- participating in associations and interest groups to underline the importance of their work
- representing the interests of the professionals towards different levels and influencing decisions

Qualification Profile for Youth Work

Operational competences

Administrative action and organisational management

1. Carrying out the administration work for the institution and organisation

Youth work professionals conduct the business of their organisation / institution in a social context by:

- taking clearly comprehensible and participative principles as a basis for the organisational structure
- comprehending administrative structures and bureaucratic procedures, acting within them in a target-oriented manner and questioning if they are situationally appropriate
- understanding organisational as well as administrative aspects as part of their work and perceiving them as a task for planning and creation
- organising and structuring work processes accordingly
- taking part in the development and assurance of quality
- knowing the relevant stakeholders and cooperating with them on the different levels (regional / cross-regional)

2. Organising financial resources

Youth work professionals organise financial resources responsibly by:

- participating in the budget planning and taking comprehensive budgetary responsibility
- acquiring financing in various contexts, employing financial means in a sustainable way and using the resources available in the social environment
- purposefully applying transparent control mechanisms and acting responsibly on these

3. Leading and managing the staff

Youth work professionals assume responsibility for the staff (also with regard to the volunteers) by:

- mentoring and coordinating staff
- being involved in the planning, recruitment and development of staff within the legal framework
- coordinating the collaboration of the different decision-making bodies
- acquainting people with new fields of activity, providing informed guidance, participating in and accompanying training
- navigating in their complex leadership position, e.g. in so-called "sandwich positions" (middle-management level)
- creating an environment with a positive work climate which enables motivated work, fosters the identification with the organisation / institution and promotes a sustainable employee loyalty

4. Carrying out public relations work

Youth work professionals carry out target-oriented public relations work by:

- continuously working on the public as well as the internal profile of their institute and organisation
- developing and coordinating strategies for effective public relations work
- cultivating diverse ways of representation of their institute and organisation

Personal competences

Apart from specialist competences, personal, social and self-competences form a fundamental essential foundation for the professional, successful action of youth work professionals. The autonomous and sustainable creation and control of complex learning and work processes in youth work are characteristic. In particular the following are key aspects.

Qualification Profile for Youth Work Personal competences Personal competences

1. Mastering challenges competently

Youth work professionals master diverse everyday and fundamental challenges by:

- using competences that are considered to result from a university education and become visible in an analytically-systematical as well as structural approach towards complex challenges
- addressing problems and facing them in a way that is proactive but also situationally appropriate using the ability to improvise and be spontaneous
- developing diverse, new and creative solution approaches and calling on other (professional) people, if necessary

2. Organising day-to-day work independently

Youth work professionals master their day-to-day work independently by:

- independently structuring and sustainably organising their work processes taking into consideration the framework conditions
- defining goals for themselves, reflecting on and evaluating the same and prioritising pending tasks accordingly
- taking part in teams and projects in a creative and responsible way
- defining limits and possibilities of their actions and constantly putting them into question

- contributing their personal interests and thereby using related competences (for example, manual, artistic, physical, (information-) technology skills)

3. Demonstrating social competence

Youth work professionals act in a particularly socially competent manner by:

- being able to constructively collaborate in teams and to expediently contribute their abilities
- cooperating with other representatives of the field as well as people from outside the field on equal terms
- in general, comprehending conflict as an opportunity, being ready to look for solutions together and to find compromises
- dealing with criticism in an open and constructive way
- possessing highly developed communicative skills, particularly dialogical, reasoning, diplomatic and rhetorical skills

4. Being able to position oneself

Youth work professionals are able to position themselves professionally and personally in different contexts by:

- possessing a highly developed decision-making ability and making situational decisions by weighing up the existing leeway of organisation and decision-making
- considering different social needs, interests of all participants and (work-)ethical aspects in their actions
- being appropriately assertive and able to set boundaries in a clear and reflected way and communicating these boundaries
- demonstrating a high level of credibility and personal confidence
- consciously drawing a line between work and private life in a way that is harmonious for them

5. Being ready to constantly learn something new

Youth work professionals are ready to repeatedly put their competences into question and to develop them by:

- possessing a profound ability to procure information and thereby organising their individual knowledge management
- having a strong learning competence based on which they view their professionalism development as an ongoing process
- recognising their personal need for further training, organising corresponding learning processes and taking suitable measures as well as reflecting on this process
- using acquired knowledge and experience to develop new possibilities for action

6. Acting responsibly

Youth work professionals act responsibly by:

- treating themselves, their needs, resources and limits in a mindful way and communicating the same
- comprehending general standards such as sustainability and equal opportunities as principles of their work
- assessing risks of their actions for themselves and others to be able to take these risks consciously in an appropriate manner

Professional self-identity

A strong professional self-identity is an important foundation for autonomous assessment, handling and evaluation of extensive professional tasks and challenges. This is the basis for the way in which complex, frequently changing, specialised challenges are faced and new strategies of action are devised, taking into account the relevant standards. As regards youth work, different competence dimensions can be differentiated: the basic pedagogical approach and the professional identity. The following aspects are particularly important in this context.

Qualification Profile for Youth Work

Professional self-identity

Professional identity

1. Identification with youth work

Youth work professionals:

- engage with the specifics and the legal duty of the field and base their actions on its basic principles: voluntariness, openness, accessibility, participation, (self-)education
- see themselves as part of social work and base their actions on its basic principles: social balance and social justice, respect for human rights, tolerance, respect for plurality and assumption of responsibility
- identify themselves with their respective institution / organisation, its supporting bodies and with the values and principles related thereto
- have a generally positive image of young people and orient themselves according to their respective resources, needs and interests
- direct their actions towards supporting young people in processes of identity development, personal development and their (self-)education (professional ethics)

2. Developing a professional understanding of roles

Youth work professionals develop an individual professional understanding of roles by:

- clarifying their personal role concerning the creation of advantageous living conditions for young people
- individually reflecting on their professional role and developing it further depending on biographical and professional contexts
- critically reflecting their professional actions as regards social expectations, consequences and from an ethical point of view
- dealing with different complex role expectations and providing situationally appropriate roles
- consciously distancing themselves from volunteers and other stakeholders in youth work as well as other fields of social work and society in their understanding of mandate and self-perception

Qualification Profile for Youth Work

Professional self-identity

Pedagogical approach

1. Embodying basic pedagogical principles

Youth work professionals embody basic pedagogical principles that are advantageous for the identity development of children, adolescents and young adults to become independent and socialised personalities (according to § 11 SGB VIII) by:

- treating young people with their specific character as well as their needs and values with acceptance, tolerance, interest and appreciation
- developing empathy for young people in their respective circumstances in life
- treating young people with openness and curiosity but also with authenticity, clear positions and reliability

2. Having critical sympathy for children and adolescents

Youth work professionals have a generally critical sympathy for children, adolescents and young adults and their respective development tasks. This is shown by the fact that:

- they take young people seriously as subjects of their own reality and development
- they generally accept and appreciate the interests and potential of young people and their respective living conditions regardless of their present behaviour
- taking their own significance seriously and reflecting on their influence on young people

3. Getting involved as a person

Youth work professionals get involved as individuals in their work by:

- being an independent, mature personality, taking a clear position, representing values and being an example of consistent action
- contributing their own interests, ideas and concepts in their work
- taking their own significance seriously and reflecting on their influence on young people

4. Positive attitude towards the resistant and the unexpected

Youth work professionals have a positive attitude towards resistance and the unexpected. This is shown by the fact that:

- they want friction and are interested in confrontation inasmuch they are generally open to critique and resistance
- they have a basic democratic attitude which perceives dialogue and negotiation processes as an important factor of coexistence
- they do not become insecure because of unexpected / unplanned events but rather accept them as challenges

5. Reflecting on their own professional action

Youth work professionals question their own professional action by:

- drawing on ethical and professional principles for critical self-reflection
- critically considering their professional action with regard to economic, social, cultural, gender and ethnic inequality
- becoming aware of the influence of their biography and of their own experience on their attitudes (and views on the world)
- realising the subjectivity of their perception, their unconscious action patterns and everyday routines

Scientific and theoretical basis

A broad and integrated knowledge and understanding for youth work, social work and relevant related disciplines are an essential basis for specialist action in youth work. The knowledge and understanding of youth work professionals are based on different previous practical and specialist experiences. Professionals have a critical understanding of theory and methods which they can draw on when reflecting on and substantiating their work. Particularly the following aspects are of fundamental importance in this complex and broad field.

Qualification Profile for Youth Work Scientific and theoretical basis Scientific and theoretical basis

1. Specific knowledge about youth work and social work

Youth work professionals base their actions on a sound understanding for youth work by:

- knowing the living environments of young people and being able to identify current living situations and challenges associated with them
- engaging with a broad spectrum of relevant topics, approaches and the history of as well as studies about youth work and being aware of reflections on the specific importance of youth work
- having a comprehensive expert knowledge of the whole field of youth work and its diverse programmes as well as of other areas of child and youth services
- addressing the issue of social work as a discipline and profession, particularly with its technical and normative foundations, its social and institutional framework conditions, its general theories of action, methods, fields of action and target groups as well as its research and possessing a broad subject and explanation knowledge

2. Key perspectives and findings of the related disciplines

Youth work professionals can draw on key perspectives and findings of the related disciplines of social work to reflect on and substantiate their own work by:

- particularly possessing relevant skills from the areas of (youth) sociology, pedagogy, psychology, philosophy and political sciences
- knowing sociological, psychological and pedagogical perspectives on children and adolescents that are related with subject, milieu, living environment and society

3. Structural knowledge

Youth work professionals possess structural knowledge by:

- knowing the institutional structures of the social and youth service system, the role of youth work therein, the political administrative structures and the framework conditions of the welfare state and are able to act within them
- concerning themselves with the general and local structures of youth work and the social-pedagogical educational offers, advisory services and offers of assistance and acting within them

4. Scientific and theoretical reference in their own work

Youth work professionals underpin their professional action with scientific and theoretical reference by:

- drawing on theoretical knowledge to interpret and classify everyday situations
- making their scientific and theoretical knowledge about theories, principles and structures usable for their practical work (theory-practice-transfer)
- working with specialised literature appropriately, making it usable for their own actions and being able to connect their findings with relevant professional discourses
- recognising procedures of academic work and possessing an extensive methodological knowledge (i.a. knowledge about the creation of concepts, quality development and project management)
- knowing different research approaches, being able to interpret studies and being able to draw on case-related and field-related analytical skills in their work (particularly ethnographical, biographical and social-spatial approaches)

5. Legal prerequisites

Youth work professionals possess a basic legal knowledge by:

- having the ability to understand legal norms and administrative regulations and being informed about amendments of law
- having knowledge about key legal correlations (particularly social legislation, SGB VIII and implementation regulations of federal state law, legal regulations about child and youth protection) and taking them into account appropriately
- aligning their values and norms with legal requirements and drawing on them in their professional actions

6. Socio-political framework conditions and developments

Youth work professionals act in consideration of social framework conditions by:

- knowing, understanding and being able to move within political structures, socio-political framework conditions and developments
- basing their decisions on knowledge about existing framework conditions and critically reflecting on them
- recognising different social distribution mechanisms, gender and generation relations, inequalities and balance of power as well as socio-cultural framework conditions and being able to develop appropriate options of action related to them

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Editor

Research project "Jugendarbeit mit Perspektive (JumP)"
University of Applied Sciences Kempten
Bahnhofstraße 61
87435 Kempten (Allgäu)

Authors

Theresa Riechert, Micha Jung, Peter Nick

Assistants

Anna Brauckmann, Daniela Fischer, Sabrina Kubick,
Alexander Köffer

E-Mail

projekt-jump@hs-kempten.de

Website

www.hs-kempten.de/JumP

Project Management

Prof. Dr. Peter Nick (University of Applied Sciences Kempten)
Prof. Dr. Patricia Pfeil (University of Applied Sciences Kempten)

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